

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN ORAL HEALTH CARE: ATTITUDES OF DENTAL PROFESSIONALS ON THE USE OF TELEDENTISTRY IN TURKEY

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Abstract

Telemedicine is transferring medical data between geographically separated areas. There are many application areas and different technologies can be used. Telemedicine has been used in medicine for many years. However, the use of telemedicine in dentistry is very little. Teledentistry has the potential to be a highly effective mechanism for enhancing early diagnosis and to be used in dental education. In a developing country such as Turkey, teledentistry is a necessity for tomorrow. This study aims to determine dental professionals' attitudes to teledentistry as means of providing consultation, diagnosis, monitoring and dental education in order to introduce teledentistry. An anonymous, self-administered survey of dental professions in Turkey was conducted by personally meeting each individual. 219 participants comprised dentists, assistants, dental students, technicians and dental educators. The data was analyzed. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and survey data. Comparisons between median Likert scale responses were performed using the Mann-Whitney U test. The authors have developed a profile of current dental professionals in the city of Ankara, i.e. the capital of Turkey. The statistical analyses demonstrate that the majority (80%) of the survey participants considered teledentistry to have potential and reported that it has to be integrated into the current dental practice. Computer use was high in this sample of Turkish dental professionals. The majority of the dental professionals participated stated that the use of teledentistry in monitoring, consultation, and education were favorable.

Keywords: Telemedicine, telehealth, teledentistry, dental professionals, dental education, Internet.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing need of communications of healthcare related data, for which the telematics development offers the best opportunities. In many cases moving the information instead of the patient is sufficient.¹ Telemedicine (and by inclusion teledentistry) has been defined in a number of ways. One definition is: "the practice of healthcare delivery, diagnosis, consultation, treatment and education using interactive audio, video or data communications" (Golder and Brennan, 2000). Although telemedicine has been practiced since the late 1950s, teledentistry is a relatively new field that combines telecommunication, informatics and dental care. The term "teledentistry" was used in 1997, when Cook defined it as "... the practice of using video-conferencing technologies to diagnose and provide advice about treatment over a distance" (Chen, Hobdell, Dunn, Johnson, Zhang, 2003). However, most dental professionals are unaware that teledentistry can be used not only for increased access to dental care but also for advanced dental education. There is a significant potential of teledentistry.

The cornerstones of modern dentistry are the deployment of the Internet and broadband high-speed connections, which have helped teledentistry enter a new era. The frontier of teledentistry is the U.S.

Army's Total Dental Access Project. Various other successful teledentistry applications were tested worldwide (Chen et al, 2003). The majority of these earlier teledentistry applications were for dental consultations, e.g. Germany, Belgium and Italy in 1996; and some were for sending patient records, videoconferencing and as a means for dental education, e.g. Scotland, Japan, England, Taiwan, and Australia (Chen et al, 2003; Cook, Austen, Stephens, 2000; Schleyer, Dasari, 1999; Farman, 2007; Mandall, O'Brien, Brady, Worthington, Harvey, 2005; Ewers, Schicho, Wagner, Undt, Seeman, Figl, Truppe, 2005; Chen, Chen, 2002).

Turkey is a developing country. Current telemedicine application efforts in Turkey are at the individual level, small sized, and are operational in few areas such as teleradiology and telepathology only. However, Turkey is aware that integrating telemedicine into its national health care program is an important element of the modernization and restructuring process currently underway. Currently there are a number of efforts for joint academic, government and industrial ventures for further development of telemedicine in Turkey. Teledentistry, however, is a completely new concept and there is no evidence showing that dentists in Turkey make use of teledentistry. According to Turkish Statistical Institute's figures for 2006, total number of dentists nationwide is 18,213 and the number of persons per dentist is 4006 (TUIK, 2006). The other important fact is that nearly half (47.2 %) of these dentists (i.e. 8595 out of 18,213) are located in the three largest cities (i.e. Ankara, Istanbul and Izmir) of the country. On the other hand, total number of physicians nationwide is 114,583, where the number of persons per physician is 637. This shows the emerging need of teledentistry awareness and its development in Turkey. This study aims to determine dental professionals' attitudes to teledentistry as means of providing consultation, diagnosis, monitoring and dental education in order to introduce teledentistry.

2 METHOD

A questionnaire was developed to obtain dental professionals' attitudes towards teledentistry. The questionnaire consisted of 3 sections and 19 5-point Likert type questions. The first section solicited general demographic and professional background information. The questions asked respondents which area in dentistry they were active in (for example, dentist, technician, assistant, student, or educator). The dental professionals involved in active patient care were asked about their practice setting, years of experience in a dental office, clinic or university hospital, patient care hours per week, and Internet access time per day and Internet access time for health related purposes. The second section of the questionnaire is to collect information about perceived understanding of the individual person regarding teledentistry. The final section is for control purposes where the overall responses are collected. The questionnaire is presented in Table 1.

After pilot testing was done with dental students, dental faculty members and technicians (n=9), the researchers got in touch personally with each individual person to fill out the questionnaire (n=230). Since the field 'teledentistry' is a new concept among the dental professionals in Turkey, with most of the survey participants, we had to explain what each of the questions in the survey meant. This is the reason that we contacted survey participants individually rather than conducting an online or email survey. The target sample was made up of randomly chosen dentists in the city of Ankara. There are four dental university hospitals in Ankara from where we have collected our dental faculty, dental students' and technicians' data. The questionnaires were distributed to dental students to be completed in class.

2.1 Data analysis

Completed questionnaires were coded and spreadsheets were created for data entry. The results were manually entered into a personal computer by a research assistant who was not aware of the study objectives. The data were 'cleaned' by checking for entries outside of legitimate ranges and inconsistent codes; the necessary corrections were made by manually rechecking the questionnaires. A random number generator was used to select 15 % of the questionnaires for hand checking by a third

party to determine the rate of data entry errors. The error rate was 0.26%, which was considered low enough to consider the remaining data accurate and forgo further manual confirmation.

The data was analyzed using SPSS (Inc. Chicago, Illinois, 60606, USA) 11.5 Windows software program. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and survey data. Comparisons between median Likert scale responses were performed using the Mann-Whitney U test. Statistical significance was determined at the $p = 0.05$ level.

Table 1. Questionnaire

Demographic
<i>Age</i>
<i>Sex</i>
<i>Years of Experience</i>
<i>Active area in dentistry:</i> Dentist (General or Specialist), Dental Assistant, Dental Student (Pre- or Postdoctoral), Educator, Technician
<i>Computer and Internet Use:</i> Average time I spend on using a computer/Internet per day is.
<i>Computer and Internet Use for Health Related Purposes:</i> Average time I spend on using a computer/Internet per day for health related purposes is.
Teledentistry perception
1. A telehealth assistant can provide me a good understanding of the patient's oral health problem over the Internet.
2. Teledentistry can violate the patient's privacy.
3. The use of necessary equipment seems difficult to me.
4. I can be as useful talking to the patient over the Internet as talking in person.
5. Teledentistry can save time for me.
6. Teledentistry can save me money.
7. Using teledentistry, I will be able to monitor my patient's condition well.
8. Teledentistry is a convenient form of oral health care delivery.
9. Teledentistry will be standard way of oral health care delivery.
10. Teledentistry can be an addition to the regular care we (the dentists) provide.
11. Teledentistry can reduce costs for the dental practices.
12. Teledentistry makes it easier for me to contact the patient.
13. I cannot always trust the equipment to work.
14. I am worried about the data entry mistakes.
Overall
15. Tele-consultation: Teledentistry will help me to consult with an expert about a specific patient's problem.
16. Tele-education: Teledentistry is good for dental education over the Internet, and for training primary care dentists.
17. Tele-monitoring: Teledentistry can help to monitor my patient's oral health.
18. Tele-surgery: Teledentistry can be used in oral surgery.
19. Overall: Overall I believe teledentistry has a potential and has to be integrated into our current dental services

3 RESULTS

Out of 230 persons contacted, 11 provided incomplete data. Therefore, 219 completed questionnaires were suitable for analysis. Demographic characteristics of the survey participants are depicted in Table 2.

Approximately half of the participants (146/219 or 67%) spent between 1-3 hours per day on the computer and Internet. Participants who spent 1-3 hours per day on the computer and the Internet were of similar age ($p=0.066$; Mann-Whitney U test) and had similar number of years' of experience ($p=0.086$; Mann-Whitney U test).

Overall, the majority of the participants were positive towards teledentistry (Question 19, 212/219 or 97%), stating that teledentistry has a potential and has to be integrated into current dental services. The

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of 219 Turkish dentists and technicians participating in the survey ^a

Characteristic	No, (%) or mean (SD)
Age (years)	35 (12.1)
Years of dental experience (n=219)	15 (10.3)
Average Internet access time (hours per day)	1-3 hours, 67%
Internet access for health related purposes (hours per day)	1-3 hours, 69%
Profession	
Dentist	
General	62
Specialist	17
Dental Assistant	7
Dental Student	
Predoctoral	83
Postdoctoral	32
Educator	12
Technician	8
Total	219

^aStandard deviation values are shown in brackets unless otherwise specified.

participants response to the use of teledentistry in teleconsulting (Question 15, 199/219 or 91%), tele-education (Question 16, 206/219 or 94%) and telemonitoring (Question 17, 178/219 or 81%) were all positive. However, 24% (or 53/219) thought that teledentistry would not be suitable for telesurgery (Question 18).

The percentage of the participants who were worried about the data entry mistakes (Question 14, 169/219 or 77%) was close to the ones who couldn't trust the equipment (Question 13, 158/219 or 72%) and these were of similar age ($p=0.074$; Mann-Whitney U test). Similarly, 39% (or 86/219) thought the use of equipment would be difficult (Question 3). 91% (200/219) of the participants see teledentistry as an addition to regular care that is currently being provided (Question 10). But only 78% (170/219) of them see teledentistry as a standard way of oral health care delivery. The responses of the participants to Question 6 (72% or 157/219) and Question 11 (66% or 144/219) show that the majority of the participants thought teledentistry would be cost-effective. 83 % (181/219) have anticipated that teledentistry would save time (Question 5). Table 3 presents the breakdown of all responses to all survey questions by profession (% of who 'agree' or 'strongly agree').

4 DISCUSSION

It is clear that the Internet has established a place in the lives of many dental professionals in Turkey. The participants in this study reported that about 77% (169/219) have used the computer and the Internet for at least 1 hour per day for health related purposes. The fact that we received responses from every category indicates that the Internet is being used by all parts of the profession.

Teledentistry is a new field that has a significant potential for supporting clinical care and for dental education (Sommer, 1995; Golder et al, 2000). It is evident from the literature that most dentists are unaware of what teledentistry is, what its goals are, and how they can get involved in it. Following is a systematic discussion on teledentistry originating from the driving forces for telemedicine (Schleyer and Spallek, 1999; Istepanian, 2001).

Table 3. Breakdown of all responses to all survey questions by profession (% of who 'agree' or 'strongly agree')

Survey Question Number	General Dentist n=62		Specialist Dentist n=17		Dental Assistant n=7		Dental Student Predoctoral n=83		Dental Student Postdoctoral n=32		Educator n=12		Technician n=8		Total n=219	
	%	Freq ^a	%	Freq ^a	%	Freq ^a	%	Freq ^a	%	Freq ^a	%	Freq ^a	%	Freq ^a	%	Freq ^a
Q1	63	39	82	14	43	3	75	62	78	25	50	6	75	6	71	155
Q2	81	50	94	16	71	5	72	60	72	23	92	11	88	7	78	172
Q3	47	29	40	7	57	4	28	23	34	11	58	7	63	5	39	86
Q4	79	49	88	15	71	5	82	68	84	27	75	9	75	6	82	179
Q5	82	51	82	14	57	4	83	69	81	26	83	10	88	7	83	181
Q6	87	54	82	14	71	5	65	54	62	20	50	6	50	4	72	157
Q7	73	45	65	11	43	3	66	55	69	22	67	8	75	6	68	150
Q8	68	42	65	11	57	4	69	57	72	23	75	9	63	5	69	151
Q9	63	39	82	14	57	4	83	69	88	28	83	10	75	6	78	170
Q10	92	57	94	16	86	6	90	75	91	29	83	10	88	7	91	200
Q11	76	47	65	11	71	5	84	70	81	26	67	8	88	7	66	144
Q12	63	39	71	12	57	4	76	63	72	23	58	7	75	6	70	154
Q13	69	43	71	12	71	5	71	59	72	23	83	10	75	6	72	158
Q14	74	46	94	16	86	6	72	60	75	24	92	11	75	6	77	169
Q15	95	59	88	15	86	6	87	72	91	29	83	10	100	8	91	199
Q16	92	57	94	16	100	7	93	77	94	30	92	11	100	8	94	206
Q17	81	50	71	12	75	5	82	68	88	28	67	8	88	7	81	178
Q18	24	15	24	4	29	2	25	21	22	7	17	2	25	2	24	53
Q19	95	59	94	16	86	6	99	82	97	31	83	10	100	8	97	212

^a 95% confidence interval

The role of teledentistry should be to optimize the gap between the increased population demand for better oral health care and existing financial resources (Bauer and Brown, 2001). In dentistry, there are fewer specialties and fewer specialists than in medicine. This fact gets more dramatic in developing countries, where the number of general dentists and dental specialists per person are low. This implies the urgent need of using resources, i.e. dental professionals, most effectively and efficiently. Overall, the results of our survey revealed that dental personnel perceive teledentistry as a means for saving cost.

Increasing diagnostic complexity requires often a peer-to-peer consultation based on data, e.g. images, i.e. **teleconsultation**. Teledentistry involves consulting experts using the Internet (Clark, 2000). The few reports are on the use of teledentistry in assessing the need for dental care during screening of elementary school children (Kopycka-Kedzierawski and Billings, 2006), in oral surgery, distance diagnosis of oral mucosal diseases (Leao and Porter, 2001), and the communication of the orthodontic advice to general dental practitioners (Cook, Mullings, Vowles, Ireland, and Stephens, 2001; Cook, Edwards, Mullings, Stephens, 2001; Stephens and Cook, 2002).

There are various application tools that were developed for teleconsultation in dentistry. For example, *Digital radiology* is an application providing films that are equivalent to traditional films for many diagnostic and therapeutic tasks (Mandall, et al, 2005; Mandall, et al, 2006; Lee, MacFarlane and O'Brien, 1999). It has many advantages such as reduced radiation exposure for patients and dental personnel, reduced development time. *OralCDx* is a method for screening oral lesions that involves a brush biopsy and computerized analysis of the histologic slide, allowing for screening of more patients for premalignant or malignant lesions earlier (Mandall, et al, 2006). These tools help to consult an expert or specialist through the available telecommunications channels, i.e. the Internet. Our study shows that the majority of the dental professionals (78%) are active computer users and they access the Internet for health related purposes, who can be trained to use these tools.

Teledentistry has the **potential for education and self-education** (Chen, et al, 2003). Respondents, especially those involved in education, reported that teledentistry would be good for dental education over the Internet and for training primary care dentists online (Question 16, 94 %). This is one of the most important application areas of teledentistry from which Turkey could benefit. Half of the dentists

in Turkey are located in the three biggest (3 out of 81) cities of the country (47.2% or 8595 out of 18,213), resulting with an inequity of oral health services available for the remaining population. It is very clear that the utilization of teledentistry for educational purposes could be significantly beneficial. The specialized dentists in these three cities can be consulted (i.e. teleconsulting) online. Whenever needed, the dental faculty (i.e. specialist dentists at university hospitals) can share clinical cases, can provide live synchronous teaching, etc. for the general dentists and for the dentists with less experience nationwide. The use of teledentistry in education would also be beneficial to the dental students in universities nationwide in regards to standardization of the course (and program) contents. The students will have access to resources online in a more systematic manner by means of a learning management system operational over the Internet. There are various teledentistry applications in dental education (Chen, et al, 2003; Schleyer and Spallek, 2001; Schleyer, 1999; Komabayashi, et al, 2005). For example, there are interactive programs providing students or practicing dentists opportunity to develop and practice their critical thinking skills for diagnosis and treatment (Schleyer and Spallek, 2001). Another example to tele-education is computer assisted learning packages on the oral manifestations of human immunodeficiency virus of relevance to general dental practitioners (Schleyer and Spallek, 2001). Such tools may be utilized in addition to making use of distance learning management systems. In Turkey, there is a mature online teaching and learning infrastructure which is exclusively run on the Internet. This infrastructure may be exploited by teledentistry, e.g. online synchronous teaching, transmission of data, images, etc., transmission of clinical cases from urban to rural parts of the country.

Teledentistry will allow independence to the way of communicating, making use of available and developing telecommunications infrastructure. The general dentist in difficult cases – when making use of telematics – discuss clinical information including images within the specialist and, because of this additional facility, the patient enjoys better care (Sanchez Dils, Lefebvre and Abeyta, 2004). This is an example to *moving the point of oral care closer to the citizen*. Teledentistry enables *equitable access to experts and specialists* with early diagnosis, i.e. telediagnosis. Teledentistry can offer improved oral health care service up to the very rural areas, considering elderly, house-bounded and underserved people; and improved oral medical care for an average patient. Treating patients in their own communities, rather than physically transporting them to the nearest qualified facility may save money (Sfikas, 1997). The literature reports a number of cases where teledentistry is utilized in patient monitoring successfully, i.e. tele-monitoring (Macdonald-Jankowski and Orpe, 2007). Nearly half of the participants of our study reported that they can be useful to and contact their patients online (Question 4, 82% and Question 12, 70%) and that they find telemonitoring useful (Question 7, 68%).

Because teledentistry allow professionals to practice across broad geographic areas, some difficult ethical, legal and regulatory concerns are raised (Sfikas, 1997; Macdonald-Jankowski and Orpe, 2007). Respondents reported their concerns in regards to violation of patient's privacy and about the confidentiality of patients' data (Question 2, 78%). These concerns arise from the electronic transmission and storage of patient's data, data entry mistakes (Question 14, 77%) and trust on the equipment (Question 13, 72%). The acceptance and use of the technology is another issue, where 39% (Question 3) respondents were concerned about the use of the equipment.

Based on the sample in this study, we cannot make generalizations for the country overall. However, the study was effective in reaching a diverse group of dental professionals in the capital city of Turkey, i.e. Ankara; and allows conclusions to be made about this sample group. To our knowledge, comparable studies have not been conducted.

5 CONCLUSION

Hitherto there has been no application of telemedicine to the field of dentistry in Turkey. This study surveyed dental professionals in Turkey, the results of which reinforce that a majority of the dental professionals in Turkey support the concept of using teledentistry integrated to current oral health care services. The responses showed that the use of teledentistry in telemonitoring, tele-education and

teleconsulting were favourable. Teledentistry programs need to be carried out in universities, teaching hospitals, and medical institutions. Collaborations between academia, government and industry should be encouraged for further exploitation of teledentistry.

REFERENCES

- Bauer JC, Brown WT. The digital transformation of oral health care. Teledentistry and electronic commerce. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2001 Feb;132(2):204-9.
- Chen JW, Hobdell MH, Dunn K, Johnson KA, Zhang J. Teledentistry and its use in dental education. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2003 Mar;134(3):342-6.
- Chen RS, Chen SK J Telemed Telecare. 2002;8(4):244-6. Teledentistry using videoconferencing and a DICOM image management system.
- Clark GT. Teledentistry: what is it now, and what will it be tomorrow? *J Calif Dent Assoc.* 2000 Feb;28(2):121-7.
- Cook J, Mullings C, Vowles R, Ireland R, Stephens C. Online orthodontic advice: a protocol for a pilot teledentistry system. *J Telemed Telecare.* 2001;7(6):324-33.
- Cook J, Edwards J, Mullings C, Stephens C. Dentists' opinions of an online orthodontic advice service. *J Telemed Telecare.* 2001;7(6):334-7.
- Cook J, Austen G, Stephens C. Videoconferencing: what are the benefits for dental practice? *Br Dent J.* 2000 Jan 22;188(2):67-70.
- Ewers R, Schicho K, Wagner A, Undt G, Seemann R, Figl M, Truppe M. Seven years of clinical experience with teleconsultation in craniomaxillofacial surgery. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2005 Oct;63(10):1447-54.
- Farman AG. Image communication: mailed, wired, and wireless. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod.* 2007 May;103(5):585-6.
- Golder DT, Brennan KA. Practicing dentistry in the age of telemedicine. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2000 Jun;131(6):734-44.
- Istepanian RS. Telemedicine in the United Kingdom: current status and future prospects. *IEEE Trans Inf Technol Biomed.* 1999 Jun;3(2):158-9.
- Kopycka-Kedzierawski DT, Billings RJ. Teledentistry in inner-city child-care centres. *J Telemed Telecare.* 2006;12(4):176-81.
- Komabayashi T, Raghuraman K, Raghuraman R, Toda S, Kawamura M, Levine SM, Bird WF. Dental education in India and Japan: implications for U.S. dental programs for foreign-trained dentists. *J Dent Educ.* 2005 Apr;69(4):461-9.
- Leao JC, Porter SR Telediagnosis of oral disease. *Braz Dent J.* 1999;10(1):47-53.
- Lee R, MacFarlane T, O'Brien K. Consistency of orthodontic treatment planning decisions. *Clin Orthod Res.* 1999 May;2(2):79-84.
- Macdonald-Jankowski DS, Orpe EC. Some current legal issues that may affect oral and maxillofacial radiology. Part 2: digital monitors and cone-beam computed tomography. *J Can Dent Assoc.* 2007 Jul-Aug;73(6):507-11.
- Mandall NA, Qureshi U, Harvey L. Teledentistry for screening new patient orthodontic referrals. Part 2: GDP perception of the referral system. *Br Dent J.* 2005 Dec 10;199(11):727-9; discussion 723. Erratum in: *Br Dent J.* 2006 Jan 28;200(2):69.
- Mandall NA, O'Brien KD, Brady J, Worthington HV, Harvey L. Teledentistry for screening new patient orthodontic referrals. Part 1: A randomised controlled trial. *Br Dent J.* 2005 Nov 26;199(10):659-62.
- Sanchez Dils E, Lefebvre C, Abeyta K. Teledentistry in the United States: a new horizon of dental care. *Int J Dent Hyg.* 2004 Nov;2(4):161-4.
- Schleyer TK, Dasari VR. Computer-based oral health records on the World Wide Web Quintessence Int. 1999 Jul;30(7):451-60.
- Schleyer T, Spallek H. Dental informatics. A cornerstone of dental practice. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2001 May;132(5):605-13. Review.

- Schleyer TK. Digital dentistry in the computer age. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 1999 Dec;130(12):1713-20.
- Sfikas PM. Teledentistry: legal and regulatory issues explored. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 1997 Dec;128(12):1716-8.
- Sommer TJ. Telemedicine: a useful and necessary tool to improving quality of healthcare in the European Union. *Comput Methods Programs Biomed.* 1995 Sep-Oct;48(1-2):73-7.
- Stephens CD, Cook J. Attitudes of UK consultants to teledentistry as a means of providing orthodontic advice to dental practitioners and their patients. *J Orthod.* 2002 Jun;29(2):137-42.
- Turkish Standards Institute (TUIK), Available online at <http://www.tuik.gov.tr> Last accessed 1st November, 2008.